

Pest management and control INSECTS

Transmission of rice yellow dwarf with the blue race of *Nephotettix virescens*

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During investigations on the transmission of rice yellow dwarf by the green leafhopper *Nephotettix virescens*, a few blue-colored adults were observed in the

rearing cages. These adults were separated and reared separately on healthy rice seedlings enclosed in clear-plastic cages. In the first generation the progeny segregated into blue and green colors. In subsequent generations, only blue leafhoppers appeared.

The transmission efficiency of rice yellow dwarf by blue- and green-colored *N. virescens* was tested. Second-instar nymphs of both blue and green *N. virescens* were collected and released separately on plants infected with rice

yellow dwarf for 24 hours of acquisition feeding. After a 30-day incubation period in the leafhoppers, 25 female and 25 male adults from each group were enclosed individually with 15-day-old healthy plants of the rice cultivar IET2295 for 48 hours. The percentage of active transmitters was 64% for blue females, 48% for blue males, 56% for green females, and 44% for green males. Therefore the blue race of *N. virescens* was as good a transmitter of yellow dwarf as the common green race. ■

Effectiveness of seedling root dip for control of gall midge

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Early planting or the use of gall midge-resistant (GMR) varieties helps reduce rice gall midge damage. When farmers are not prepared to grow GMR varieties and also must plant late, chemicals (granular systemic insecticides) are the only available means of protection. But most chemicals are too costly for the average farmer.

A seedling root dip, if effective, should be economical. Although prophylactic in nature, it would fit into a system of integrated pest control because of its low cost and its ecological selectivity (seedling dip would have little adverse effect on natural enemies of gall midge).

In our preliminary pesticide screening trials, we found the insecticides chlorpyrifos and isofenphos promising for use in seedling root-dip treatment (Table 1).

In another experiment, we further tested those insecticides in both plain water and a 1% urea solution. The dipping time of 1 hour was extended to 3 hours.

The dipping in 0.02% isofenphos for 12 hours was most effective (Table 2). But when isofenphos was used with 1.0% urea, reduction of the dipping time

Table 1. Percentages of silver shoots, productive tillers, and sound grains and average yield of rice variety Jaya under different seedling root dip treatments to control rice gall midge. Raipur, India.^a

Treatment	Dipping time (h)	Silver shoots (%) at 30 DT ^b	Productive tillers (%) at harvest ^c	Sound grains (%)	Yield (t/ha)
Untreated check		47.4 c	45.7 e	62.4	1.8 de
Isofenphos 0.02% in water	12	39.0 bcde	56.1 abcd	66.3	2.6 bc
Isofenphos 0.02% in water	1	40.0 cde	46.8 d	67.8	1.9 cde
Isofenphos 0.02% in 1% urea solution	12	35.4 bcd	48.4 d	63.4	2.3 bcd
Isofenphos 0.02% in 1% urea solution	1	29.7 ab	52.6 cd	60.5	2.6 b
Isofenphos 0.04% in water	12	23.3 a	64.6 a	57.1	3.5 a
Isofenphos 0.04% in water	1	41.9 de	48.3 d	63.0	1.5 e
Isofenphos 0.04% in 1% urea solution	12	29.8 abc	54.8 abcd	61.4	2.2 bcd
Isofenphos 0.04% in 1% urea solution	1	32.8 abcd	63.4 ab	61.1	2.2 bcd
Chlorpyrifos 0.02% in water	12	33.8 bcd	60.2 abc	61.6	2.3 bcd
Chlorpyrifos 0.02% in 1% urea solution	12	35.9 bcd	50.7 cd	64.3 ns	2.1 bcd

^aIn a column, any 2 means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% level. ns = not significant. ^bDays after transplanting. ^cAngular transformed value.

Table 2. Percentages of silver shoots, productive tillers, and sound grains and average yield of rice variety Jaya under different seedling root dip treatments^a to control rice gall midge. Raipur, India.

Treatment	Dipping time (h)	Silver shoots (%) at 30 DT ^b	Productive tillers (%) at harvest ^c	Sound grains (%)	Av yield (t/ha)
Isofenphos 0.02%	12	14.5 a	70.1	67.6	2.2 a
Isofenphos 0.02% in 1% urea solution	3	15.3 a	59.9	70.1	1.8 ab
Chlorpyrifos 0.02%	12	20.8 b	62.6	67.5	1.5 bc
Chlorpyrifos 0.02% in 1% urea solution	3	14.4 a	59.8	67.2	1.4 bc
Untreated check		36.6 a	59.9 ns	64.78 ns	1.2 c

^aIn a column, any 2 means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% level. ns = not significant. ^bDays after transplanting. ^cAngular transformed values.

to 3 hours was equally effective. Chlorpyrifos was not effective.

Seedling root dip of isofenphos or

chlorpyrifos had no effect on grain filling. Isofenphos 0.04% was most effective when dipping time was 12 hours,

but was ineffective, regardless of concentration, when dipping time was reduced to 1 hour. ■

Efficacy of granular insecticides on different developmental stages of brown planthopper

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A literature review reveals that almost nothing is known about the effect of granular insecticides on the developmental stages.

Laboratory experiments with 9 granular insecticides were carried out on 1-month-old potted plants of varieties Taichung Native 1. Test insecticides at 1 kg a.i./ha were applied in standing

water. A circular polythene sheet was placed on the water surface so the stem passed through a central hole while the upper part of the plant stood in its natural position. The treated plants were caged in transparent plastic tubes and 6 individual stages of the brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* were released on the test plants. Each treatment was replicated four times. The mortality caused by individual insecticides was recorded 48 hours after the insects were released.

The table indicates that nymphs of the first and second instars were highly susceptible to AC 64475, carbofuran, phorate, and isofenvinphos; those of the

third instar were highly susceptible to the first three.

For the fourth- and fifth-instar nymphs, carbofuran and phorate were most effective. Among adults, the females were comparatively less susceptible than the males. However, both were highly susceptible to carbofuran and phorate. The mortality caused by the other insecticides at all the active stages was significantly less.

Overall, carbofuran, phorate and AC 64475 were most effective because they resulted in high mortality in all the active stages of *N. lugens*. Quinalphos, fenitrothion, and fenthion registered low mortality. ■

Mean percentage of mortality of different stages of *N. lugens* due to granular insecticides. Pantnagar, India.

Insecticide	Mortality (%)							
	First-instar nymph	Second-instar nymph	Third-instar nymph	Fourth-instar nymph	Fifth-instar nymph	Adult male	Adult female	Mean
AC 64475	100.0 (90.0)	100.0 (90.0)	100.0 (90.0)	95.0 (80.0)	92.5 (76.2)	97.5 (85.4)	87.5 (72.1)	96.1 (83.5)
AC 92-100	79.4 (63.4)	71.7 (58.1)	67.5 (55.4)	55.0 (47.9)	50.0 (45.0)	60.0 (50.8)	45.0 (42.1)	61.2 (51.8)
Carbofuran	100.0 (90.0)	100.0 (90.0)	100.0 (90.0)	100.0 (90.0)	100.0 (90.0)	100.0 (90.0)	100.0 (90.0)	100.0 (90.0)
Fenthion	61.4 (51.3)	52.8 (46.6)	42.5 (40.7)	40.0 (39.2)	32.5 (34.7)	45.0 (42.1)	20.0 (26.2)	42.0 (40.2)
Fenitrothion	46.1 (42.8)	35.8 (36.7)	40.0 (39.2)	30.0 (32.9)	25.0 (29.9)	27.5 (31.4)	15.0 (22.5)	31.3 (33.6)
Isofenvinphos	100.0 (90.0)	100.0 (90.0)	85.0 (67.5)	85.0 (67.5)	72.5 (58.5)	82.5 (67.5)	87.1 (65.6)	87.1 (72.4)
Mephosfolan	92.2 (75.9)	68.6 (56.0)	60.0 (50.8)	50.0 (45.0)	50.0 (45.0)	55.0 (47.9)	52.0 (46.4)	61.2 (52.4)
Phorate	100.0 (90.0)	100.0 (90.0)	100.0 (90.0)	97.5 (85.4)	97.5 (85.4)	100.0 (90.0)	100.0 (90.0)	99.3 (86.7)
Quinalphos	38.6 (38.4)	35.0 (36.2)	28.9 (32.5)	22.5 (28.3)	8.1 (16.1)	8.1 (16.1)	4.4 (11.4)	20.8 (25.6)
Control	2.5 (9.1)	2.5 (9.1)	2.5 (9.1)	2.5 (9.1)	2.5 (9.1)	2.5 (9.1)	2.5 (9.1)	2.5 (9.1)
Mean	72.0 (64.4)	67.6 (60.3)	62.6 (56.2)	57.8 (52.6)	53.1 (48.9)	58.1 (53.0)	50.9 (47.5)	

Data in parentheses are angular transformed values.
C.D. at 5%

Insecticide (I) (2.44)
Stages (S) (2.04)
Interaction (I × S) (6.46)

Potential wind-assisted migration by planthoppers in the Philippines

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Long-distance migration, assisted by wind, may play a part in the development of planthopper populations in the tropics as it does in Japan and Korea.

A suction trap, 11 m above the ground, monitors daily aerial activity

over a 2-ha rice plot at Liliw (Philippines) near IRRI, in a study of the effect of migration on insect population dynamics at the site. A peak catch of both brown planthoppers and white-backed planthoppers was recorded when the trap was emptied on the morning of 15 October 1979. The captured insects could have originated at the site or immigrated from other rice areas. The airborne planthoppers encountered windspeeds of about 3-9 km/hour. This

is probably greater than their flight speed. In such winds, the track of the planthoppers would tend to be the same as that of the air in which they were flying.

With the use of weather maps to determine the airflow above the Philippines, it is possible to simulate the movement of planthoppers captured 14-15 October. To illustrate the potential displacements, the tracks of planthoppers taking off from or arriving at